

D4.1: Map existing and emerging requirements for interoperability in XR and Spatial Computing

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ABSTRACT:	This report aims to provide the current state of interoperability in the eXtended Reality (XR) and spatial computing field and assesses its emerging requirements. We employed Systematic Literature Review (SLR) method to examine and map the current state of interoperability standards, frameworks, guidelines, and identify the limitations to elicit future requirements.
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1. Introduction

This report is the first of the two deliverables of work package 4. The main goal of WP4 is to co-create an Interoperability Guidance Document. The first objective of achieving this goal is to map existing and emerging requirements for interoperability in XR and spatial computing – effects on accessibility – existing and emerging challenges – emerging requirements – including an overview of existing, emerging, and new Standards. Deliverable 4.1(D4.1) will provide an overview of the state of the art of interoperability and preliminary assessment of relevant frameworks, surveys, guidelines, white papers, standards within in XR and Spatial Computing. D4.1 is meant to serve the purposes of other WPs, such as but not limited to, WP3, WP5 and WP6. For this purpose, we have employed Systematic Literature Review (SLR) to examine and map the current state of interoperability standards, frameworks, guidelines, identify the limitations and elicit future requirements.

1.1 Background

Extended Reality (XR) and spatial computing technologies are evolving rapidly and transforming various industries such as education, entertainment, gaming, healthcare, communication, manufacturing, etc. While these technologies continue to develop at a rapid pace, the lack of interoperability between XR hardware, applications, and platforms is becoming a huge issue.

LAYERS OF THE SPATIAL WEB

Figure 1. Layers of spatial web (Open AR Cloud Europe gUG adjusted and updated version 2023)

There's still no universal definition of Interoperability within XR and Spatial Computing. The World Economic Forum defined it as «The ability to interact, exchange and make use of data and resulting information to enable movement, transactions and participation across systems, platforms, environments, and technologies. » (World Economic Forum, 2022; their Interoperability White paper).

Interoperability: Moving from a set of independent platforms and services to an integrated network of real-time reality capture layer or 3D virtual worlds. Interoperability and interchangeability across servers and clients through existing and emerging standards, frameworks, and guidelines. Clients and server implementations respectively without worrying about compatibility and compliance or authentication, just like today's Web runs multiple Webservers, browsers, and the edge with standards, such as OpenID and OauthOpenAuth. Interoperability of content and experiences across solutions, as well as scalability.

This lack of interoperability leads to less accessibility for users and data, making the technology adaptation more challenging. To solve this issue and make the technology more interoperable and accessible to the European population and stakeholders, the project aims to create guidelines for interoperability (WP4). As the first task in this work package (WP4), this report aims to provide an overview of the existing and emerging requirements for interoperability in XR and Spatial Computing through a Systematic Literature Review (SLR). The review maps the current landscape of interoperability in XR and limitations in literature for creating an interoperability guide that should help provide seamless integration and collaboration in XR and spatial computing.

The next era of computing/Web is approaching quickly, the so-called "Internet in Everything, the transformation of the Internet from ICT to a control network embedded directly into the physical world for operating systems and devices across every sector and industry, a potential more consequential shift than even the industrial revolution or the information age before."^[1]

Dominant technology companies such as Apple, Meta (Facebook), and Google, Niantic, Snap, and other big tech giants have been gradually enclosing online, or virtual spaces by bringing all manner of products and services into their walled gardens through vertical integration and control. As we transition more and more into this post digital era, leveraging interoperability cross systems and platforms are key.

1.2 Aim and objectives

The aim is to provide an overview of the current state of interoperability, existing and emerging standards, guidelines, surveys frameworks, white papers, and best practices related to XR and spatial computing.

The main objectives of this report are to

- Map the current state of Interoperability in XR, from an XR infrastructure perspective, platforms, and systems.
- Create awareness of lack and limitations of interoperability in the XR and spatial computing community/Industry and how this affects the development of XR solutions as well as accessibility.
- Assess whether interoperability affects accessibility in XR and spatial computing.

Specific Objectives:

- To assess the existing state/landscape of interoperability within XR and spatial computing
- To identify, address and identify issues/challenges and emerging requirements.

2. Methods

The methodology utilised for this report is Systematic Literature Review (SLR). SLR is a method of identifying, evaluating, and interpreting available research relevant to a particular research question or topic area. SLR provides a higher degree of confidence about covering the relevant literature, and thus minimizes the subjectivity and bias through reproducible results (Kitchenham et al., 2010). We have carried out the SLR based on the guideline from Kitchenham (2004).

The following sub-sections detail the steps in the SLR process implemented in this report, including the research questions, search strategy, inclusion/exclusion criteria, data extraction and synthesis of results.

2.1 Research Questions

Important first step of the SLR process is defining the scope of the review and research questions. Table 1. shows the defined scope of review through the PICOC framework (Booth, Sutton, & Papaioannou, 2016).

Table 1. PICOC framework

PICOC Element	Definition
Population	<u>Participants</u> : Users, developers, stakeholders, and policy makers in the XR and spatial computing industry. <u>Devices</u> : XR and spatial computing hardware devices (e.g. HMDs, PCs, Handheld devices such as tablets and smart phones). <u>Applications</u> : XR and spatial computing software applications, platforms and services.
Intervention	Standards, frameworks, guidelines and protocols for interoperability in XR and spatial computing. Emerging technologies and solutions for improving interoperability.
Comparison	Existing interoperability solutions and standards. Different XR ecosystems and platforms.
Outcomes	Assess and map the current interoperability standards in XR. Evaluate the impact of emerging technologies on XR interoperability. Understand user experiences and satisfaction with interoperable XR solutions. Identify challenges and barriers to achieving interoperability.
Context	The technological landscape and advancements in XR and spatial computing. Regulatory and privacy considerations in XR interoperability.

Based on the above-defined scope, the following research questions (RQs) were formulated:

RQ1: What is the current state of Interoperability in XR from an infrastructure, platforms, and systems perspective?

This RQ aims to address the status of existing and emerging standards for interoperability in XR and spatial computing.

RQ2: Is there a growing awareness of the lack of interoperability in the XR community/Industry?

This RQ aims to document the discussions in literature about the challenges of lack of interoperability and how does that affect the development of XR solutions as well as accessibility.

RQ3: How does interoperability affect the development of XR solutions, accessibility, and policy making?

Currently, XR and spatial computing landscape is comprised of both open and proprietary solutions. This RQ aims to find evidence for accessibility being affected by interoperability.

2.2 Search Strategy and Process

We selected 5 different interdisciplinary research databases for the search (Web of Science, OVID, IEEE Xplore, ETSI, ISO, OGC). These databases were identified as relevant for review because of the technical and standards heavy nature of the scope of review. Additional searches were carried out in Google Scholar for snowballing references.

We performed the search in the above databases using the following search string. The search term for this review combined the terms for interoperability, extended reality, spatial computing in conjunction with terms for platforms and guidelines.

```
( TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( Interoperability" ) AND ( framework* OR guideline* OR guidance* AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ( interactive W/2 ( media* OR experience* ) ) OR metaverse OR XR OR ( immersive W/2 ( technolog* OR environment* ) ) OR ( virtual W/2 ( reality OR environment* ) ) OR ( virtualiz* OR virtualis* ) W/2 ( technolog* OR network* ) ) OR ( augmented or AR W/2 reality ) OR ( mixed or MR W/2 reality ) OR ( extended or XR W/2 reality ) OR ( Spatial* W/2 comput* ) )
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2.3 Eligibility Criteria

Considering the research questions, in the general criteria, the time frame for study and relevant type of study were defined.

General Criteria:

- Research articles, standards published between January 1st, 2012, and February 31st, 2023.
- Research articles, standards, surveys guidelines, and frameworks that cover interoperability in XR and spatial computing.

Specific Criteria:

- Primary studies that evaluate the effectiveness of current interoperability practices in XR and spatial computing
- Primary studies/standards that represent the current interoperability state-of-the-art in XR and spatial computing.
- Secondary studies/literature review that document interoperability research status in XR and spatial computing
- Studies, documents covering technology, emerging tech, software, services, platforms for interoperability.

The following exclusion criteria were defined:

- Documents that are not published in English.
- Documents that were published before 2012.
- Grey literature, ex. project reports, technical reports
- Tutorials and poster publications
- Documents that don't discuss interoperability from technical and human perspective.
- Documents that are not related to/applied for interoperability in XR and spatial computing.
- Studies that discuss medical, health, pharmaceutical, animal and biology related interoperability

After completing search, initial de-duplication was done in the reference management software Zotero. The identified references were then exported to the systematic review tool Rayyan for the screening and selection process. In this phase, the documents found in the searching phase were reduced by applying the eligibility criteria. Two researchers filtered through the document titles, keywords, and abstracts by applying inclusion and exclusion criteria filters. Based on the consensus between the two researchers in Rayyan, full-text articles for the final review were selected. These full-text articles were then reviewed for eligibility by two researchers and the final articles to be included in the review were selected.

2.4 Data Collection and Extraction

The selected final articles were then imported to a data extraction sheet in an Excel file. The following data were extracted from the final articles based on the defined PICOC framework:

- Bibliographic information of the publication
- The targeted audience for the publication
- The application domain and context of the document
- The main problem addressed by the document and the outcomes
- The objectives/challenges addressed in the document
- The method and metrics used for measuring the outcome

3. Results

This section presents the results of the review, answering the three research questions based on the extracted data from the 48 number of documents over a publication period of the past 10 years. Figure 2 presents the selection process based on the pre-established framework.

3.1 Synthesis of results

Figure 2. Results of the selection process (Flow diagram)

This section dives deep into the results obtained from the 46 papers screened mapping the state of the art of interoperability within XR and Spatial computing and addresses the emerging requirements needed to strengthen and build up on its existing components.

3.1.1 XR standards current state of Interoperability (RQ1)

Within this systematic review we've been primarily interested in what the primary literature (standards, frameworks, guides, articles, and papers) already proposes and established to push broader establishment of interoperability within XR and spatial computing to improve XR production processes for content creators and developers on a global scale.

After screening and further analysing the documents, the selected 46 papers. We gained further insights into the current state of interoperability within XR and spatial computing from frameworks, guidelines, recommendations, and emerging and already established standards to further advance its status in a diverse range of fields.

Approximately 80% of the selected papers were issued between 2020 and 2022, and more than 30 papers were published between 2021-2023. They primarily address interoperability standards. The main stakeholders were developers, creators, and policymakers. Twelve of the papers proposed frameworks related to interoperability, while 9 were guidelines and white papers proposing methods to increase establishing interoperability within XR/spatial computing.

RQ1 aims to address the status of existing and emerging standards for interoperability in XR and spatial computing. During detailed analysis process, 6 different types of papers were identified (Figure 3)

Figure 3. different types of papers and overview of the number of publications.

Most findings not only addressed the growing interest in XR but also proved the lack and current fragmentation of interoperability between systems, platforms and data formats and its adoption, its improvement of production processes, which go hand in hand with calls for interoperability in XR and its impact. (IEEE survey, 2022). Further stating to avoid market fragmentation, create a level playing field that provides access to new markets, and through economies of scale, which can help reduce costs for all: manufacturers, service providers, and consumers. Additionally, a couple of the papers provided hands-on, applicable solutions and guidelines, which led to emerging standards or limitations and combined with other findings, to broader sustained impact work.

The literature review shows that its establishment is way more complex due to the context-based nature of these emerging technologies and their intersection and influence by others. Even though on the one hand, it shows the vast existence of established and acceleration of emerging universal standards and guidelines, on the other hand, the search proves its limitations. Each limitation is a critical indicator for emerging requirements needed – which proves and is a key indicator for the lack of interoperability. More actions to constantly advance and new ones are needed to make them even more accessible and applicable to a wide range of stakeholders.

Thus, the following are needed to establish an XR and spatial computing interoperability mentality:

1. building capabilities for XR interoperability by establishing common understanding, guidelines, frameworks that are direct (standard terminology), identifying key system and user requirements (design guidelines and system standards) and developing compatible interfaces and data formats for XR services and applications; and
2. defining XR user experience requirements addressing accessibility and quality aspects.

In this section, we introduce a selection of existing technical standards and specifications, grouped by theme, relevant to the creation, delivery, and deployment of XR experiences.

The terminology is often the first element to be standardized for any new technology as it provides the foundation for interoperability. Current work on standard terminology for XR tends to feature more within standards offering guidance on other topics under the XR umbrella, as in the case of [1], rather than standalone lexicons such as CTA-2069-A.

Sharing digital content among these applications is challenging, although many of them have the same development platform and original 3D model. This paper reviewed XR applications in the lifecycle of a construction project and summarized key information requirements for 3D models, development software systems, and processes for information transfer. Results show that a generic and adaptable model that satisfies these requirements can streamline the development process of different XR applications in the same project. Creating a generic model does not require additional activities. Instead, it relocates model pre-processing activities at the beginning of the XR development and precludes repetitive activities when possible. This paper contributes to the body of knowledge by specifying the requirements of a generic model that enhanced the interoperability of digital assets among XR technologies and applications (Model Requirements for the Development of Extended Reality Applications in Construction Projects: A Literature Review, 2022)

3.1.2 XR Growing awareness of interoperability (RQ2)

This RQ2 aims to document the discussions in the literature about the challenges of lack of interoperability and how that affects the development of XR solutions as well as accessibility. The team analysed the 46 papers to gain and provide the necessary overview of a growing awareness of the lack of interoperability within XR and spatial computing by investigating the number of broad variety of publications and its year of publication (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Trend of volume of publications

According to IEEE Survey 2022, a growing interest in and adoption of XR go hand in hand with calls for interoperability, to avoid market fragmentation, create a level playing field which provides access to new markets, and through economies of scale, which can help reduce costs for all: manufacturers, service providers, and consumers. Therefore, in response to RQ2, Figure 4 presents the topic covered and its growing awareness in relation to the number of publications since 2021, implying an increase of awareness, of establishing and advancing interoperability within XR and the broader spatial computing technology infrastructure, including limitations, and barriers.

3.1.3 Affecting development of solutions, accessibility and policy making (RQ2)

Two papers surprisingly addressing the broader impact/effect of intersecting technologies, data layers, formats, and processes that are influenced by interoperability.

Others are human/design, policy, safety, and ethical influences directly or indirectly affecting and influencing Interoperability within XR and spatial computing, addressing a different perspective of inter-complexity that was gained during the search analysis.

Experience management layer

Stakeholder participation layer

Data and infrastructure layer

Considerations

Interoperability guidance, standards, best practices, etc. at each level should consider three key areas:

- Technical interoperability
- Usage interoperability
- Jurisdictional interoperability

These apply to places within the metaverse and stakeholders' assets, data and identity(s).

Figure 5. Layers of interoperability and considerations (World Economic Forum 2023)

The Study on Standardization for the Metaverse on the proposes two types of Interoperability classification (see the following three graphics): vertical interworking and horizontal interworking. Through horizontal interworking, the metaverse platform interacts with other metaverse platforms or 3rd party service platforms, and synchronization with the physical world can be achieved through vertical interworking.

Horizontal interworking can be seen as a way for users to seamlessly move and experience multiple metaverse platforms. For this, content, real-time events, user profiles, device profiles, etc. need to be exchanged. Vertical interworking is mainly for synchronization between the real world and the virtual.

Figure 6. Direct interaction model between Metaverse Service Providers (Study on Standardization for the Metaverse, 2023)

Figure 7. Indirect interaction model through Metaverse Integration Service Providers (Study on Standardization for the Metaverse 2023).

Figure 8. General purpose client (Study on Standardization for the Metaverse 2023).

3.2 Summary and Discussion

The goal of this systematic search and literature review was to gain a fundamental understanding of the current state of Interoperability and Spatial Computing within XR and identify issues and limitations to address and define emerging requirements needed. We chose the PICOC methodology to gain knowledge from a wide range of literature. We had a pre-determined search and eligibility criteria; we identified 46 relevant documents between 2012 and 2023 restricted to only English. Defining the themes of the analysis within a data extraction sheet to filter out standards, frameworks, guidelines, and best practices within interoperability and gain an understanding of interoperability issues existing to define and develop emerging requirements needed.

3.3 Interoperability Issues (limitation and gaps)

The growing interest in and adoption of XR go hand in hand with calls for Interoperability to avoid market fragmentation, create a level playing field that provides access to new markets, and through economies of scale, which can help reduce costs for all: manufacturers, service providers, and consumers. During the analysis process of this work, we have identified a large and diverse range of interoperability limitations. One big interoperability problem today in XR technology is the lack of interoperability between users' existing digital life (including 2D documents, videos, the Web, and even mobile applications) and the

3D spaces that are the core of XR. Without such interoperability, 3D spaces offered by current XR platforms and service providers seem empty, lacking in functionality.

Effects of lack of interoperability: On the other hand, it is necessary to point out that the widespread adoption of XR still faces some challenges, which mostly have to do with the practicality of the technology in terms of its ability to integrate with users' existing digital lives seamlessly. Although XR has the potential to go further than just provide appealing visual experiences by influencing how information is encountered, understood, retained, and recalled by users (Csapó et al., 2018; Horvath and Sudar, 2018), this is only possible if a data-driven spatial experience is emphasized first and foremost.

Despite the advantages of 3D spaces, both in general and in MaxWhere, a key obstacle in terms of integrating 2D content into 3D spaces is that users cannot change the existing 2D layouts (comfortably or at all), thus their thinking is forced into the constraints of the currently existing layouts, leading to reduced effectiveness and ease of use. However, it is also clear that no single layout is suitable for all tasks. In MaxWhere, it is often the case that users report their desire to add "just one more smartboard" to a space or to "move this smartboard next to the other one" for clearer context.

Due to the intersection and convergence of emerging technologies, a focus is on establishing interoperability or reusability when utilizing different domains, for example, XR and IoT. IoT has been developed and aligned to standards by itself, while the ones addressing interoperability limitations within XR are being developed with a different focus based on its isolated needs. These different characteristics between the development processes of IoT and AR/MR may cause interoperability problems when combined and served for common use.

4 Beyond results

4.1 Current State of Standards

During the reviewing process of the literature, we gained additional knowledge of existing and emerging standards work accelerated by well-known standard organizations and new emerging initiatives that underlines the need for advancement of universal guidelines and standards across emerging technologies and XR. However, its existence and knowledge are still fragmented due to missing links and activities between them.

New recent initiatives pushing interoperability within XR/Spatial Computing aim to provide standards and common solutions. They have just started their work and therefore have not delivered anything yet.

The Alliance for Open USD (AOUSD):

Based on the existing framework established by Pixar's USD. The Alliance for Open USD (AOUSD) launched during Siggraph 2023 and was formed by its founding members Adobe Autodesk, Apple, Pixar, and NVIDIA; private entities joined forces to establish a standard that will enable easier workflows for content creators, optimization, and distribution, through broad adoption within rendering software, the XR industry should closely follow its further advancements.

DIN: XR, Web3.0 and Metaverse standard group:

Started its work with the official kick off on October 24th 2023

Metaverse Standards Forum:

Initiated by the Khronos Group in June 2022, the Metaverse Standards Forum intends to bring together companies and standards organizations to foster alignment on requirements and priorities for metaverse interoperability standards and accelerate their development and deployment. Rather than developing standards itself, the forum's goal is to coordinate requirements and support for existing standards relevant to the metaverse, and to provide a venue for discussion and coordination between standards organizations and companies building metaverse-related products. Membership is currently at no charge and open for for-profit and non-profit organizations, including universities.

The Khronos group:

An industry consortium creating interoperability standards for 3D graphics, AR, and VR, among other areas. The Khronos membership also includes some 20 universities.

XR API suite provides developers with tools to create interoperable XR experiences (OpenXR) and generate 3D scenes/assets (3DCommerce and glTF), and high-performance low-latency 3D graphics (Vulkan, OpenGL and WebGL).

Standard groups and established initiatives:

W3C's Immersive Web Working Group is aiming to bring XR content, applications, and services to the web by developing standardized APIs to interact with XR devices and sensors in web browsers. W3C is hosted jointly by four academic institutions and is continuously further developing technologies that can provide high performance through the support of WebXR, WebVR, WebAsm and WebGPU. It is though still difficult to see the direction of standardization especially in the recently found Community Groups which have been founded 2022.

Metaverse Interoperability Community Group

Galaxy Meravers Community Group Virtual Reality website and Metaverse

European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI):

The European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) is a recognized regional standards body dealing with telecommunications, broadcasting and other electronic communication networks and services. ETSI's Industry Specification Group (ISG) Augmented Reality Framework (ARF) aims to specify relevant components and interfaces required to ensure interoperability of AR components, systems, and services. ETSI specifies a functional reference architecture (ETSI GS ARF 003) and detailed interoperability requirements (ETSI GS ARF 004-x series) for AR components, systems, and services in addition to the requirements described in ETSI GR ARF 002.

XR use cases have been described across a range of standards-related literature (both normative and informative publications) including SVTA's extended reality brief, VRIF's guidelines on live VR services, multiple 3GPP technical reports including TR 26.862 (immersive teleconferencing), TR 26.928 (XR services in 5G), TR 26.918 (VR use cases) and TR 26.998 (AR use cases over 5G), an ETSI report (ETSI GR ARF 002) on AR industrial use cases and specifications (ETSI GS MEC 002 and GS MEC-IEG 004) on XR over mobile edge computing, as well as a few ITU Recommendations including ITU-T G.1036 (AR use cases) and ITU-T H.430.3 (use cases on Immersive Live Experiences (ILEs)).

Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineering Standard Association (IEEE SA):

IEEE SA work on XR-related topics is spread across several committees, working groups and projects, including:

- IEEE VR/AR Standards Committee (CTS/VRARSC),
- IEEE 1857 Working Group (Audio Video Coding),
- IEEE P2048 Working Group (VR/AR),
- IEEE P2843 Working Group (Measuring Accessibility Experience and Compliance),
- IEEE P2874 Working Group (Spatial Web protocol, architecture and governance), in collaboration with the Spatial Web Foundation,
- IEEE 2888 Working Group (Interfacing cyber and physical world),
- IEEE 3079 Working Group (Human factors for immersive content),
- IEEE P7030 Working Group (Global XR ethics).

Standards offer guidance on deploying specific XR use cases such as IEEE 1589 (AR-assisted learning), ITU-T F.740.2 (AR artwork) and ITU-T J.301 (AR-enabled smart television services).

The adopted definitions for AR in a sample of standards converge towards a uniform interpretation of AR as a superimposition of virtual objects to the "real"/physical world. ITU-T P.1320 as well as CTA-2069-A and CTA-2085 standards altogether outline key terms for XR and could potentially be used in combination as a "comprehensive XR glossary". Ongoing work under IEEE P2048, which aims to define terminology for immersive video, audio, and VR/AR devices, could also complement this list once complete.

Immersive Digital Experiences Alliance (IDEA)

The Immersive Digital Experiences Alliance (IDEA) is an industry alliance working towards developing royalty-free technical specifications that define interoperable interfaces and exchange formats to support the end-to-end conveyance of immersive volumetric and/or light field media.

From the ISO/IEC suite, ISO/IEC 23090-8 defines APIs for immersive media processing and the extensible 3D (X3D) standards provide a format and architecture for the representation of 3D scenes/objects (ISO/IEC 19775 and 19776 series). Specific formats for XR are also defined within (ISO/IEC

18038-18040, and 18520,23488).

4.2 Human - interoperability

By reviewing existing regulatory frameworks and policy guidelines created in Web 2.0 and analyzing how existing laws around relevant topics – like online safety and content moderation – are also being applied to XR and broader Spatial computing. Before adjusting and using it within context-based technologies, which are way more layered and therefore can't be applied on a one-on-one scale. Various factors need to be considered before doing so.

Some of the frameworks and guidelines found as part of our search analysis proposed a more User/developer-human-centred approach. We built up on these findings to adjust and align them to our XR4Human project to have them reflect and align with the ethical and legal work packages, which intersects with the tasks we tackled within the tasks of the XR and Spatial computing work package, and its deliverables. See the proposed topics in Figure 9 to further complex, layered components to align XR and spatial computing interoperability with human-centred design.

Figure 9. Holistic human-centered interoperability clustering.

Figure 10. SOTEF LOOP: Lifecycle of a human-centred interoperable XR system.

4.3 Outlook Universal guidelines for Interoperability

As a next step during the WP4.2 task, we will further assess the knowledge gathered within this deliverable and develop a Universal Interoperability Guide. Here, we aim to exceed the requirements by providing a tool tailored to the main stakeholders and needs, making current standards, guidelines, and frameworks more accessible and applicable to each processes.

A knowledge representation and reasoning, a knowledge graph is a knowledge base that uses a graph-structure data model or topology to integrate data. Knowledge graphs are often used to store interlinked descriptions of entities - objects, events, situations, or abstract concepts - while also encoding the semantics underlying the used terminology¹. Since the development on the Semantic Web, knowledge graphs are often associated with linked open data projects, focusing on the connections between concepts and entities. They are also prominently associated with and used by search engines such as Google, Bing, Yext, and Yahoo; knowledge-engines and question-answering services such Wolfram Alpha Apple's Siri, and Amazon Alexa; and social networks such as LinkedIn and Facebook.

Figure 11. Look out to WP4.2 Deliverable Interoperability knowledge graph tool draft JASON prototype screenshot.

With this knowledge graph visualizer, we aim to not only understand the relationships between the different elements that are needed to create interoperable XR and spatial computing solutions, but enable different elements that are needed to create interoperability XR solutions, but enable different stakeholders and objective functions to intuitively navigate through the graph extracting the information that it is relevant for their specific context and needs.

5 Conclusions

The performed literature review states the lack of and existing fragmentation of Interoperability in XR and spatial computing to date. The literature review shows that its establishment is way more complex due to the context-based nature of these emerging technologies and their intersection and influence by others. Even though on the one hand, it shows the vast existence of established and acceleration of emerging universal standards and guidelines, on the other hand, the search proves its limitations. More actions to constantly advance and occur new ones are needed to make them even more accessible and applicable to a wide range of stakeholders.

While these barriers seem to be familiar to the ones faced within the Web 2.0 era, there are additional ones, such as the lifecycle and maintenance of big data sets referring to digital twins or 3D maps of the physical world. We lack convention paths. The kicked-off work started by the Open USD group providing an interoperable data format standard between gltf and USD could be an excellent example for others.

The findings propose different methods of how Interoperability is applied to XR and spatial computing to establish a seamless connection with policymaking and integration of human-centred design to improve creation and achieve more frictionless development processes. This could be achieved by clustering Interoperability into

- Technical Interoperability
- Human-centred/ User Interoperability
- Policy and legal Interoperability

Finally, this deliverable primarily aimed to get an understanding of the current state of interoperability of XR and Spatial computing to outline its emerging requirements.

Even though there are already standards and a growing acceleration of groups and initiatives joining forces to establish new ones and build upon existing ones focusing on the interoperability of XR and spatial computing (pushed by a growing awareness of the effect interoperability has on XR and spatial computing). It is important to emphasize that this knowledge and emerging solutions need to be made more accessible to push for further and broader adoption of these technologies. Additionally, they need to be built and assessed to be more applicable for developers and creators.

Future advancements of standards and frameworks should aim to improve processes across industry and data formats, which is a growing need due to the convergence of technology solutions and production processes cross-industry.

Technical standards such as glTF, and/or universal scene description USD and the current open USD initiative are a great example on how the support of data interchange pushes interoperability across the existing XR and spatial computing infrastructure. Future best practices should cover functional usage and technical data interchange cross industries due to the growing convergence of technologies affected.

Furthermore, we need a more holistic perspective on interoperability within XR and spatial computing shifting to take on a more human-centred and jurisdictional approach. This shift of perspective will have a broader effect on the whole development and establishment of XR and spatial computing standards, frameworks, and guidelines but even for policy making, data and infrastructure design, broader participation, and adoption of emerging technologies and XR.

Based on our findings and analysis, we need to state that, establishing and maintaining interoperability depends not just on data interchange across infrastructures to enable participants' ability to access, move, transact, and create within and across digital (and physical) worlds. It is necessary that we establish collaboration and an interdisciplinary approach not only on the creation and development layer but also on a standard, policy, and management layer due to the convergence of emerging technologies that are already affecting the development and creation processes.

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